

Non-archimedean Fuzzy Topological Spaces

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Abstract:

In this paper we define for fuzzy topological spaces a notion corresponding to non-archimedean topological spaces. We obtain some properties of these fuzzy topological spaces, particularly we prove a result on fuzzy metrizability.

Keywords:

c-zero dimensionality, fuzzy point, crisp fuzzy set, quasi-coincident fuzzy sets, fuzzy base, *N*-compactness, fuzzy metrizability.

1. Introduction

An important subclass of zero dimensional spaces is the class of non-archimedean topological spaces, introduced by A.F. Monna [9]. A topological space X is said non-archimedean if there exists a base $\mathcal{B}$ for X such that for any pair $B_1, B_2 \in \mathcal{B}$ with non-empty intersection we have either $B_1 \subset B_2$ or $B_2 \subset B_1$.

In 1965 L.A. Zadeh [13] introduced the theory of fuzzy sets, and in 1968 C.L. Chang [4] defined the fuzzy topology. Following these researches, much fuzzy concepts have been defined and studied by divers mathematicians. We introduce in this paper the notion of non-archimedean fuzzy topological space. Our definition is based on the concept of *c*-zero dimensionality of N. Ajmal and J.K. Kohli [1]. We investigate some properties of non-archimedean fuzzy topological spaces and among others we obtain a result on fuzzy metrizability.

2. Preliminaries

First, we summarize the definitions which we will use along this paper.
The set X is always non-empty.

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Definition [11, 13]. A function A from X to the unit interval $[0,1]$ is called a fuzzy set in X . The set $\{x \in X \mid A(x) > 0\}$ is called the support of A and is denoted by $\text{supp } A$. If A takes only the values 0, 1, A is called a crisp set in X .

Definition [13]. Let $\{A_j \mid j \in J\}$ be a family of fuzzy sets in X . Then the union $\bigvee_{j \in J} A_j$ and the intersection $\bigwedge_{j \in J} A_j$ are defined, respectively, by:

$$\left(\bigvee_{j \in J} A_j\right)(x) = \sup_{j \in J} \{A_j(x)\}, \quad x \in X$$

$$\left(\bigwedge_{j \in J} A_j\right)(x) = \inf_{j \in J} \{A_j(x)\}, \quad x \in X.$$

If A is a fuzzy set in X , the complement of A , denoted by A' , is defined by $A'(x) = 1 - A(x)$, $x \in X$.

Definition [11]. Let (X, T) be a fuzzy topological space. A subfamily $\mathcal{B}$ of T is called a base for T if, for each $A \in T$, there exists $\mathcal{B}_A \subset \mathcal{B}$ such that $A = \bigvee_{B \in \mathcal{B}_A} B$.

Definition [11]. A fuzzy set in X is called a fuzzy point if it takes the value 0 for all $y \in X$ except one, say, $x \in X$. If its value at x is λ ($0 < \lambda \leq 1$) we denote this fuzzy point by x_λ .

Definition [11]. A fuzzy point x_λ is said to be quasi-coincident with A if $\lambda > A'(x)$. This is denoted by $x_\lambda q A$.

Definition [11]. A is said to be quasi-coincident with B , if there exists $x \in X$ such that $A(x) > B'(x)$. This denoted by $A q B$.

Definition [11]. A fuzzy set A in (X, T) is called a Q -neighborhood of x_λ if there exists a $B \in T$ such that $x_\lambda q B \subset A$.

Definition [1]. A fuzzy topological space (X, T) is called c -zero dimensional if every crisp fuzzy point x_1 in X and every fuzzy open set U containing x_1 there exists a crisp fuzzy set B in X such that $x_1 \in B \subset U$.

Definition [7]. Let (X, T) be a fuzzy topological space and $\mathcal{A}$ be a family of fuzzy sets in X . The family $\mathcal{A}$ is called locally finite in X if for each point e in X there exists a Q -neighborhood U of e such that is quasi-coincident with only finitely many members of $\mathcal{A}$.

Definition [6]. Let (X, T) be a fuzzy topological space. If A is a subset of X , then we denote χ_A its characteristic function. The set $[T] = \{A \subset X \mid \chi_A \in T\}$ is called the original topology of X .

Definition [8]. A fuzzy topological space (X, T) is called a weak induction of the topological space (X, T_0) if $[T] = T_0$ and each $U \in T$ is lower semi-continuous from (X, T_0) to $[0, 1]$.

3. Non-archimedean fuzzy topological spaces

Definition 1. A fuzzy topological space (X, T) is said to be non-archimedean if there exists a base $\mathcal{B}$ for T by clopen crisp fuzzy sets such that for any pair B_1, B_2 of quasi-coincident members of $\mathcal{B}$, we have either $B_1 \subset B_2$ or $B_2 \subset B_1$. These fuzzy bases will be said non-archimedean fuzzy.

Remark 3.0. All non-archimedean fuzzy topological space is c -zero dimensional fuzzy.

Proof. If U is an open fuzzy containing a crisp fuzzy point x_1 , then $U(x) = 1$. Thus there exists a member B of a non-archimedean fuzzy base for X such that $B(x) = 1$, and $x_1 \in B \subset U$.

Proposition 3.1. Let (X, T) be a non-archimedean fuzzy topological space. Then, each fuzzy open set in X is a characteristic function.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{B}$ be a non-archimedean base fuzzy for (X, T) . For every $A \in T$ there exists a subfamily $\mathcal{B}_A \subset \mathcal{B}$ such that $A = \bigvee_{B \in \mathcal{B}_A} B$.

We have that for each $x \in X$

$$A(x) = \sup_{B \in \mathcal{B}_A} \{B(x)\} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } B(x) = 1 \text{ for some } B \in \mathcal{B}_A \\ 0 & \text{if } B(x) = 0 \text{ for all } B \in \mathcal{B}_A \end{cases}$$

Then A is crisp and $A = \chi_{\text{supp } A}$.

Proposition 3.2. Let (X, T) be a non-archimedean fuzzy topological space, and $(X, [T])$ its weak induction. Then $(X, [T])$ is non-archimedean topological space.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{B}$ be a non-archimedean fuzzy base for (X, T) , then $\mathcal{B}^* = \{B \subset X \mid \chi_B \in \mathcal{B}\}$ is base for $(X, [T])$. Indeed, for each $A \in [T]$, $\chi_A \in T$ and $\chi_A = \bigvee_{j \in J} \chi_{B_j}$ for some subfamily $\{\chi_{B_j} \mid j \in J\} \subset \mathcal{B}$. Thus

$$\chi_A = \chi_{\bigcup_{j \in J} B_j} \text{ and } A = \bigcup_{j \in J} B_j$$

where

$$\{B_j | j \in J\} \in \mathcal{B}^*.$$

Finally $\mathcal{B}^*$ is non-archimedean base for $(X, [T])$ because if $B_i \in \mathcal{B}^*$, $i=1,2$ with $B_1 \cap B_2 \neq \emptyset$, then $\chi_{B_1}(x)=1$ for some $x \in X$, $\chi_{B_1}(x) > \chi_{B_2}(x)$ and χ_{B_1} is quasi-coincident with χ_{B_2} . Then the non-archimedean property of $\mathcal{B}$ yields that $\chi_{B_1} \subset \chi_{B_2}$ or $\chi_{B_2} \subset \chi_{B_1}$. Thus $B_1 \subset B_2$ or $B_2 \subset B_1$.

Remark 3.3. A weakly induced fuzzy topological space (X, T) of a non-archimedean topological space (X, T_0) need not be non-archimedean fuzzy.

Let (X, T_0) be the Michael line $\mathbb{R}_Q$. It is non-archimedean [10, Example 1] and there are continuous functions from $\mathbb{R}_Q$ to $[0, 1]$ which are not characteristic function.

Lemma 3.4. Let (X, T) be a non-archimedean fuzzy topological space and $\mathcal{B}$ a non-archimedean base for it. Let $\mathcal{C}$ be a chain in $\mathcal{B}$ (i.e., a totally ordered subfamily of $\mathcal{B}$, ordered by inclusion). Then the union of the members of $\mathcal{C}$ is clopen fuzzy set in X .

Proof. By Proposition 3.2 we have that $\mathcal{B}^* = \{B \subset X | \chi_B \in T\}$ is a non-archimedean base for the weak induction $(X, [T])$.

If $\mathcal{C}$ is a chain in $\mathcal{B}$, clearly $\mathcal{C}^* = \{B | \chi_B \in \mathcal{C}\}$ is chain in $\mathcal{B}^*$, then by [10, Lemma 2], it follows that $\bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{C}^*} B$ is clopen. Thus $\chi_{\bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{C}^*} B} = \bigvee_{B \in \mathcal{C}^*} \chi_B$ is clopen fuzzy.

Lemma 3.5. Let (X, T) be a non-archimedean fuzzy topological space and $\mathcal{B}$ a non-archimedean base for it. Then, also the family of the unions of the members of chains in $\mathcal{B}$, is a non-archimedean base for (X, T) .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{B}^* = \{B \subset X | \chi_B \in T\}$. The chains $\mathcal{C}^* = \{B | \chi_B \in \mathcal{C}\}$ of $\mathcal{B}^*$ verify that $\bigcup_{B \in \mathcal{C}^*} B$ is clopen and for any two such unions D_1, D_2 we have either $D_1 \cap D_2 = \emptyset$, $D_1 \subset D_2$ or $D_2 \subset D_1$. Thus, if χ_{D_1} is quasi-coincident with χ_{D_2} , we have either $\chi_{D_1} \subset \chi_{D_2}$ or $\chi_{D_2} \subset \chi_{D_1}$.

Proposition 3.6. Let (X, T) be a non-archimedean fuzzy topological space, then there exists a base $\mathcal{B}$ for (X, T) such that if χ_A is a fuzzy set in X , thus χ_A is clopen fuzzy if and only if χ_A is the union of a pairwise non quasi-coincident locally finite in X , subfamily of $\mathcal{B}$.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{B}_0$ be a non-archimedean base for (X, T) and $\mathcal{B}$ the set of all unions of chains in $\mathcal{B}_0$.

χ_A is clopen fuzzy set in (X, T) if and only if A is clopen in $(X, [T])$. By [10, Theorem 3] this is equivalent to let A be the union of locally finitely many disjoint basis sets of $\mathcal{B}$.

If $A = \bigcup_{j \in J} D_j$ with $\{D_j | j \in J\} \subset \mathcal{B}$ pairwise disjoint and locally finite in $(X, [T])$, then $\chi_A = \bigvee_{j \in J} \chi_{D_j}$ with $\{\chi_{D_j} | j \in J\} \subset \mathcal{B}^* = \{\chi_B | B \in \mathcal{B}\}$. For each fuzzy point x_λ in χ_A if $x \in A$, then $x \in D_{j_0}$ for only $j_0 \in J$. Thus $x_\lambda \in \chi_{D_{j_0}}$ and $x_\lambda \not\in \chi_{D_n}$ for only j_0 . And χ_{D_n} is not quasi-coincident with χ_{D_j} if $j \neq j_0$. For a fuzzy point $x_\lambda \notin \chi_A$ the result is clear because χ_A is closed fuzzy.

Conversely, if χ_A is the union of a pairwise non quasi-coincident locally finite in X , subfamily of $\mathcal{B}$. Let $\chi_A = \bigvee_{j \in J} \chi_{D_j}$, then $A = \bigcup_{j \in J} D_j$ and if $x \in A$, then $x \in \chi_A$. Thus for only a $j_0 \in J$ is $\chi_{D_{j_0}}(x) = 1$, then $x \in D_{j_0}$ which does not intersect any other member of $\mathcal{B}$. If $x \notin A$, then it is clear because A is closed.

Proposition 3.7. *Let (X, T) be a fuzzy topological space such that all fuzzy open set in X is a characteristic function. Then (X, T) is non-archimedean fuzzy topological space if and only if $(X, [T])$ is non-archimedean topological space.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{B}$ be a non-archimedean base for $(X, [T])$, then $\mathcal{B}^* = \{\chi_B | B \in \mathcal{B}\}$ is base for (X, T) . Indeed, for each $\chi_A \in T$ if $A \in [T]$, then $A = \bigcup_{j \in J} B_j$ and $\{B_j | j \in J\} \subset \mathcal{B}$. Thus $\chi_A = \chi_{\bigcup_{j \in J} B_j} = \bigvee_{j \in J} \chi_{B_j}$ and $\{\chi_{B_j} | j \in J\} \subset \mathcal{B}^*$. Finally, $\mathcal{B}^*$ is non-archimedean fuzzy because χ_{B_1} quasi-coincident with χ_{B_2} for $\chi_{B_i} \in \mathcal{B}^*$, $i = 1, 2$, yields that $\chi_{B_1}(x) > 1 - \chi_{B_2}(x)$ for some $x \in X$, then $\chi_{B_1}(x) = 1 > 0 = 1 - \chi_{B_2}(x)$ for some $x \in X$, thus $x \in B_1 \cap B_2$ and by the non-archimedean property of $\mathcal{B}$, we have either $B_1 \subset B_2$ or $B_2 \subset B_1$. Then $\chi_{B_1} \subset \chi_{B_2}$ or $\chi_{B_2} \subset \chi_{B_1}$.

The converse is by Proposition 3.2.

Definition 2. A base $\mathcal{B}$ for a fuzzy topological space (X, T) such that every subfamily $\mathcal{B}'$ satisfies either

- (1) $\bigwedge_{B \in \mathcal{B}'} B$ is open fuzzy or
- (2) $\bigwedge_{B \in \mathcal{B}'} B$ is a fuzzy point, and $\mathcal{B}'$ is a base for the Q -neighborhoods of it will be called a fuzzy ortho-base for (X, T) .

Proposition 3.8. *Let (X, T) be a non-archimedean fuzzy topological space. Then (X, T) has a fuzzy ortho-base.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{B}$ be a non-archimedean fuzzy base for (X, T) . By Proposition 3.2, $\mathcal{B}^* = \{B \subset X | \chi_B \in \mathcal{B}\}$ is non-archimedean base for $(X, [T])$. If $\mathcal{B}_1$ is a subfamily of $\mathcal{B}$, then $\mathcal{B}_1^* = \{B \subset X | \chi_B \in \mathcal{B}_1\} \subset \mathcal{B}^*$. Thus either

- (1) $\bigcap_{B \in \mathcal{B}_1^*} B$ is open in $(X, [T])$ or
- (2) $\bigcap_{B \in \mathcal{B}_1^*} B$ is a point x , and $\mathcal{B}_1^*$ is a base for the neighborhoods of x , by [3. Lemma 4].

If we have (1), then $\bigwedge_{\chi_B \in \mathcal{B}_1} \chi_B = \chi_{\bigcap_{B \in \mathcal{B}_1} B} \in T$.

If we have (2), then $\bigwedge_{\chi_B \in \mathcal{B}_1} \chi_B = \chi_{\{x\}} = x_1$ crisp fuzzy point in X . Finally for every $\chi_A \in T$ such that $x_1 \in \chi_A$ if $\chi_A(x) = 1$, then $x \in A \in [T]$ and there exists $B \in \mathcal{B}_1^*$ such that $x \in B \subset A$. Thus $\chi_B \in \mathcal{B}_1$, $x_1 \not\leq \chi_B \subset \chi_A$ and $\{\chi_B \mid \chi_B \in \mathcal{B}_1\}$ is base for the Q -neighborhoods of x_1 .

Definition 3. A fuzzy topological space such that every open fuzzy covering of its has a locally finite refinement by clopen fuzzy sets, will be called an ultraparacompact fuzzy topological space.

Proposition 3.9. *Every non-archimedean fuzzy topological space is ultraparacompact fuzzy topological space.*

Proof. Is analogous to [10, Theorem 4]. For each fuzzy point x_λ in X , let W_{x_λ} be the union of all fuzzy sets B , such that $x_\lambda \in B \in \mathcal{B}$ and $B \subset U$, for some $U \in \mathcal{U}$ (where $\mathcal{B}$ is a non-archimedean fuzzy base and $\mathcal{U}$ an open fuzzy covering). Since B is crisp, we have that $\lambda = 1$ and by the non-archimedean property of $\mathcal{B}$, W_{x_λ} is the union of a totally ordered set of basis sets, and therefore, by Lemma 3.4, clopen. For any x_1, y_1 fuzzy points in X we have either $W_{x_1} \cap W_{y_1} = \emptyset$ or $W_{x_1} = W_{y_1}$. So the set $\mathcal{W} = \{W_{x_1} \mid x_1 \text{ crisp fuzzy point in } X\}$ covers X , but it does not necessarily refine $\mathcal{U}$.

Let $W \in \mathcal{W}$, if $W \subset U$ for some $U \in \mathcal{U}$, let $W \in \mathcal{W}^*$. Otherwise, in the chain $\mathcal{C} = \{B \mid x_1 \in B \in \mathcal{B}, B \subset U \text{ for some } U \in \mathcal{U}\}$ we let $\{V_\alpha \mid \alpha \in A\}$ be a well-ordered cofinal subchain. Let $W_\alpha = V_\alpha \sim \bigvee_{\beta < \alpha} V_\beta$. By the well-ordering and cofinality $\{W_\alpha \mid \alpha \in A\}$ covers W , its members are disjoint and they are clopen since $\bigvee_{\beta < \alpha} V_\beta$ is clopen by Lemma 3.4. Finally, for each α , $V_\alpha \subset U$ for some $U \in \mathcal{U}$, then $W_\alpha \subset U$.

Proposition 3.10. *Every N -compact non-archimedean fuzzy topological space (X, T) has an uniform non-archimedean fuzzy base (i.e., there exists a non-archimedean fuzzy base such that for each fuzzy point $x_1 \in X$ and each fuzzy open U , $x_1 \in U$, only a finite number of members of this base contain x_1 and are quasi-coincident with U).*

Proof. If (X, T) is a N -compact non-archimedean fuzzy topological space, then there exists a non-archimedean fuzzy base $\mathcal{B}$ for it, and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{B \subset X \mid \chi_B \in \mathcal{B}\}$ is a non-archimedean base for its weak induction $(X, [T])$ which is compact [12, Theorem 3.6]. By [10, Theorem 7] $\mathcal{B}^*$ is uniform and this yields that $\mathcal{B}$ is uniform fuzzy base (indeed, if x_1 is a fuzzy point in X contained in a fuzzy open set χ_U of (X, T) and there are $\{\chi_{B_n} \mid n \in \mathbb{N}\} \subset \mathcal{B}$ such that $x_1 \in \chi_{B_n}$ and $\chi_{B_n} \wedge \chi_U \neq \emptyset$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then $x \in U$, $x \in B_n \in \mathcal{B}^*$, and $B_n \cap (X \setminus U) \neq \emptyset$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and this is contradictory because $\mathcal{B}^*$ is uniform).

Proposition 3.11. *Every N -compact non-archimedean fuzzy topological space is metrizable fuzzy.*

Proof. Let (X, T) be a N -compact non-archimedean fuzzy topological space, then (X, T) is S^* -paracompact [7, Theorem 2.7] and has an uniform non-archimedean fuzzy base, by the above Proposition. Then $(X, [T])$ is paracompact [7, Corollary 3.7] and has an uniform base (indeed if $\mathcal{B}$ is uniform fuzzy base for (X, T) , then $\mathcal{B}' = \{B \subset X \mid \chi_B \in \mathcal{B}\}$ is uniform base for $(X, [T])$). Thus, by a metrization theorem of Alexandroff [2], $(X, [T])$ is metrizable, and finally (X, T) is metrizable fuzzy, by a result of Eklund and W. Gähler [5].

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